

Site: SPHINX TEMPLE Season GS 79-80

Area: N-Colonnade Square R16A Locus Number ② (2a)

Progress of Excavation 16/7/80 At end of day ② taken out from N Balk R16 to cut edge through ②-③-③b half way to N wall (see plan). ②a-②b originally thought to be part of ② but clearance of ② to cut edge revealed ①a over ①b (①b as dried crust) and ①b over ②. ② and ③ clean sand thought to be mod. when cleared R16 W side trench. But important to know if ② fill of ancient interruption of ④-④d. Therefore ② taken out 16/7/80 sifted 17/7/80. 17/7/80: Begin by taking out ①a-①b to N. S.T. Wall. No indication of mod. inclusions in most of ② taken up 16/7/80 end of day. →

Locus Description Greyish sand w/ limestone frags (comes up brown when damp)

Location in Square WRONG. Phasing out half way from R16 N Balk to N S.T. Wall // 17/7/80 12:30. ② R16 (2a in R16A) continues to N wall, embanked against, over ③: clean tan sand.

Under Locus ①-①b Over Locus ③ CLEAN SAND

Locus Dimensions _____

Levels _____

Analysis of non-artifactual materials Med. to small and fine limestone frags. Few granite frags and dolerite chips.

17/I/80. What was cleared as (2) on 16/I/80 (and in R16) shows darker grey band phasing out after edge of disturbance 65cm from R16 N Balk under this the lighter greyish buff sand w/ many limestone flecks. Packer band in photo designated (2) - lighter greyish buff (over (3) clean sand) as (2a)

SEE REVERSE SIDE LOCUS SHEET (1a) - (1b)

* WHEN LOCI finally straightened out 11:00-12:00 17/I/80, (2a) (2) R16) taken back to N wall to reveal (3) clean sand embanked against (3b) - Tan clay compact sand. All 2-2a sifted. Band of darker more compact tan moister (clay-like?) runs along S.T. N wall Designated (3c)

23/I/80: After 5 days of no work, exposed surface (2) - (2a) brushed clean and planned. Wonder now if below (3) in R16 (3b) - (3c) N Balk not darker more compact also slightly tan-clay like, i.e. (3b)?

Decided to clear back to another cross-sub balk to get relation of (3) to (3b) - (4) again.

* (2) - (2a) has limestone material, large chunks to small fine frags, particles. Large frags not saved.